

**THE PROGRESS OF UZBEK SPORTS IN THE REFORM PERIOD
(IN THE EXAMPLE OF NAVOI REGION)**

Abstract:

The article describes the reforms implemented in the field of sports in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the decisions made and their implementation, as an example of the achievements of athletes in the Navoi region.

Key words:

physical education and sports, Ministry of Tourism and Sports, sports education system, Indore hockey, sports competitions, kickboxing.

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Today, in the rapidly developing world, sport is one of the main factors in increasing the national prestige of countries at the international level. Physical culture plays an important role in human health and increases labor productivity. Cultural changes, industrialization and urbanization processes taking place in the world are one of the factors that ensure the growth of sports. For this reason, developed countries are developing their own programs to popularize physical education and sports. Several projects are being developed and implemented by the International Olympic Committee and the International Sports Organization (FIFA) in developed and developing countries. In particular, increasing the role of physical culture in strengthening the health of the population, standardizing the methodology of sports games, and organizing systematic sports competitions are among them.

In Uzbekistan, the field of physical education and sports is one of the areas that receive the most attention. Effective mechanisms for promoting a healthy lifestyle among the population, ensuring that our country has a worthy place in international sports arenas, as well as the construction of physical education and sports facilities, capital repair and equipment of existing ones is being done.

The establishment of the Ministry of Tourism and Sports in 2021 led to the improvement of the management of the sector. In particular, the adoption of the concept of physical education and mass sports development in 2019-2023 serves to ensure the effectiveness of reforms in the sector and increase the reputation of the republic in international sports competitions.

Therefore, in all regions of our republic, great attention is paid to the field of physical education and sports. Including in Navoi region. As the President admitted, every region should have schools for athletes who have achieved high results.

Decision PQ-5280 of the President of November 5, 2021 "On the program for the development of sports and educational institutions until 2025" was adopted.

The document confirmed the following:

- Program for the development of the activities of sports and educational institutions until 2025 and the "Road Map" for the implementation of the Program in 2021-2022;
- Target indicators (indicators) of the program;
- The main parameters of the construction, reconstruction, perfect repair and equipment of Olympic and Paralympic reserve college facilities in 2022-2025.

The program was developed in order to ensure the implementation of the decision No. PQ-5160 dated 25.06.2021. It defines the following as the main directions of development of the sports education system:

- qualitatively updating the content of the sports education system, as well as training, retraining and improving the qualifications of professional pedagogues;
- improvement of the teaching methodology, step-by-step implementation of the principles of individualization in the educational process;
- to improve the quality of sports services provided by athletes to persons with physical disabilities and disabilities;
- development of effective mechanisms to eliminate elements of corruption in the sports education system;

- strengthening the material and technical base of sports educational institutions and increasing the effectiveness of their financial support, etc.

Imported by the Ministry of Tourism and Sports, not produced in the Republic of Uzbekistan, according to the lists formed in accordance with the established procedure for equipping and organizing the activities of sports educational institutions and the Institute of Retraining and Advanced Qualification of Physical Education and Sports Specialists, the Institute of Physical Education and Sports Scientific Research equipment, special vehicles, multimedia products, medical simulators, literature, artificial and natural surface coverings and inventories will be exempt from customs duty until October 1, 2024.

According to the schedule of competitions of the Ministry of Tourism and Sports of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Field Hockey Federation of Uzbekistan for 2022, on February 4-9 of this year in the city of Navoi, Navoi region, the first indoor ice hockey tournament of 2001 will be held. The competition of the Cup of Uzbekistan among teenagers born in 2016 and younger has ended. A total of 7 teams participated in this competition. Teams from Tashkent region, Andijan region, Namangan region, Khorezm region, Samarkand region and Navoi region participated. A total of 114 athletes participated in the competition. According to the final results of the competition

Honorable 1st place: Samarkand region team

Honorable 2nd place: team of Tashkent region and

Honorable 3rd place was won by the team of Navoi region. At the end of the competition, the participants of the winning teams were awarded by the Ministry of Tourism and Sports of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Field Hockey Federation of Uzbekistan, and the Navoi Region Tourism and Sports Department of the children-adolescent sports school specialized in sports and athletics. They were awarded diplomas and souvenirs.

On May 4-6, 2022, an athletics competition dedicated to the memory of R.Kudratov was held in Tashkent. Sportsmen-students of the athletics department of the Children's and Adolescent Sports School specializing in sports and athletics of the Navoi Region Sports Development Directorate took part in this competition. Competition results:

Sports school students Farkhod Salokhidinov and Dilshodbek Bobokulov became the new Uzbekistan record holders in the 400 meter race.

Athletes of our region at the Handball Championship of Uzbekistan

With the 2nd place, they were admitted to higher educational institutions with preferential treatment.

The Asian Kickboxing Championship is currently being held in Bangkok, the capital of Thailand. A. Sodikov and his coach D. Khojamov, a student of the Kyziltepa district sports school of Navoi region, are participating in this competition. Uzbek athletes won 10 medals at the Asian Championship. 4 gold and 6 silver medals. D. Khojamov from Navoi became the champion of Asia.

As we can see, the athletes of Navoi region have a worthy place in the development of sports in Uzbekistan and in the recognition of the world.

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